

1 **Evaluating the Base Excision Repair Inhibitor TRC102 and Temozolomide for patients**
2 **with Recurrent Glioblastoma in the Phase 2 Adult Brain Tumor Consortium Trial BERT**
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58

- 59 • **Supplementary Figure S1:** Supportive Preclinical Data
- 60 • **Supplementary Figure S2:** Signaling Pathway Impact Analysis of recurrent
61 glioblastoma patients in the BERT trial.
- 62 • **Supplementary Figure S3:** Correlation between MGMT mRNA and MGMT protein
63 abundance values in glioblastoma from the CPTAC database.
- 64 • **Supplementary Figure S4:** Correlation between MPG mRNA and MPG protein
65 abundance values in glioblastoma from the CPTAC database.
- 66 • **Supplementary Figure S5:** Correlation between MGMT and MPG protein levels in
67 glioblastoma from the CPTAC database.
- 68 • **Supplementary Figure S6:** Association between MGMT and MPG mRNA levels in
69 newly-diagnosed glioblastoma patients from the TCGA database.
- 70 • **Supplementary Figure S7:** Association between MGMT and MPG mRNA levels in
71 recurrent glioblastoma patients from the CCGA database.
- 72 • **Supplementary Table S1:** Key Resources Table
- 73 • **Supplementary Table S2:** Representativeness of Study Representativeness
- 74 • **Supplementary Table S3:** Adverse Events in the BERT trial
- 75 • **Supplementary Appendix S1:** Final Amended Version of the Clinical Trial Protocol

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77

78 **Abstract**

79 **Purpose:** Patients with glioblastoma (GBM) have a dismal prognosis. While DNA alkylating agent
80 temozolomide (TMZ) is mainstay of chemotherapy, therapeutic resistance develops rapidly in
81 patients. Base excision repair inhibitor TRC102 (methoxyamine) reverses TMZ resistance in
82 preclinical glioma models. We sought to investigate efficacy and safety of oral TRC102+TMZ for
83 recurrent GBM (rGBM).

84 **Patients and Methods:** A pre-registered (NCT02395692), non-randomized, multicenter, phase 2
85 clinical trial (BERT) was planned and conducted through the Adult Brain Tumor Consortium
86 (ABTC-1402). Arm 1 included bevacizumab-naïve GBM patients at first recurrence, with primary
87 endpoint of response rates. If sufficient activity was identified, a second arm was planned in
88 bevacizumab-refractory patients. Secondary endpoints were overall survival (OS), progression-
89 free survival (PFS), PFS at six months (PFS-6), and toxicity.

90 **Results:** Arm 1 enrolled 19 patients with median of two treatment cycles. Objective responses
91 were not observed, hence, arm 2 did not open. Median OS was 11.1 months (95%CI 8.2-17.9).
92 Median PFS was 1.9 months (95%CI 1.8-3.7). PFS-6 was 10.5% (95%CI 1.3-33.1%). Most
93 toxicities were Grade 1-2, with two Grade 3 lymphopenias and one Grade 4 thrombocytopenia.
94 Two patients with PFS \geq 17 months and OS >32 months were deemed ‘extended survivors’. RNA
95 sequencing of tumor tissue, obtained at diagnosis, demonstrated significantly enriched signatures
96 of DNA damage response (DDR), chromosomal instability (CIN70, CIN25), and cellular
97 proliferation (PCNA25) in ‘extended survivors’.

98 **Conclusions:** These findings confirm safety and feasibility of TRC102+TMZ for rGBM patients.
99 They also warrant further evaluation of combination therapy in biomarker-enriched trials
100 enrolling GBM patients with baseline hyperactivated DDR pathways.

101

102 **Keywords:** Methoxyamine, TRC102, BER inhibitor, glioblastoma multiforme, high-grade glioma,
103 N-methylpurine DNA glycosylase; MPG; TMZ

104

105 **Translational Relevance:**

106

107 In this multicenter, phase 2 trial conducted through the NCI Adult Brain Tumor
108 Consortium in patients with recurrent glioblastoma (rGBM), DNA alkylating agent
109 (temozolomide) combined with DNA base excision repair inhibitor (TRC102) was found to be
110 safe and feasible for further evaluation in biomarker-enriched trials. A subset of patients
111 benefitting from TRC102+TMZ was observed, in whom RNA sequencing of tumor tissue
112 collected at diagnosis demonstrated significant enrichment for gene signatures of DNA damage
113 response (DDR), chromosomal instability (CIN70, CIN25), and cellular proliferation (PCNA25).
114 This DDR signature was found present in nearly 10% of all newly diagnosed glioblastoma patients
115 in the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA). Findings of this trial demonstrate a potential for better
116 patient selection for therapeutic targeting using a hyperactivated DDR gene signature. They also
117 provide insights into the context of tumor vulnerability to synthetic lethality generated with the
118 combination of a DNA damaging agent and DNA repair blockade.

119 **Introduction**

120 Glioblastoma (GBM) is the most common primary brain malignancy in adults.¹ It is also
121 the most aggressive malignant brain tumor, with minimal therapeutic advances made in the last
122 decade.² Despite standard of care therapy, 2- and 5-year overall survival (OS) rates remain 27%
123 and 9.8%, respectively.³⁻⁵ while the median time to progression continues to be nearly seven
124 months.³ Recurrence is nearly inevitable, for which no standard efficacious therapies currently
125 exist. Salvage chemotherapies are largely ineffective, associated with median progression-free
126 survival (PFS) at 6-months (PFS-6) rates of 10-15%.⁵ Bevacizumab, while being FDA-approved
127 for recurrent GBM based on response rates, has not led to a significant increase in survival.^{6,7}
128 Additionally, survival after the failure of bevacizumab administered in this setting is dismal, with
129 a median survival of 4-6 months and PFS-6 of zero.⁸ Hence, novel therapies for recurrent GBM
130 are urgently needed.

131 Temozolomide (TMZ), one of the rare pharmacological successes in the past few decades
132 in GBM is the most commonly used chemotherapeutic agent, resulting in a survival benefit of 2-3
133 months.^{3,4} This second-generation alkylating agent causes DNA damage by attaching mutagenic
134 adducts to tumor DNA leading to the generation of O⁶-methylguanine (O⁶-mG), N³-
135 methyladenine (N³-mA) and N⁷-methylguanine (N⁷-mG) base lesions. The N³-mA and N⁷-mG
136 adducts are repaired through base-excision repair (BER). The O⁶-mG adducts, the most cytotoxic
137 lesions produced by TMZ, are repaired by mismatch repair (MMR) through O⁶-mG-DNA
138 methyltransferase (MGMT).⁹ MMR's failure to fix O⁶-mG-thymine pairs results in long-lived
139 DNA nicks and cell cycle inhibition. Thus, tumor sensitivity to TMZ is contingent upon low
140 MGMT and MMR activity.

141 TMZ resistance is a critical element in GBM treatment failure.¹⁰ Resistance is secondary
142 to increased rates of DNA repair, which occur either due to enhanced levels of repair proteins or
143 defects in the MMR pathway.^{10,11} MGMT promoter demethylation permits increased MGMT
144 expression followed by greater DNA repair, leading to rapid development of TMZ resistance and
145 tumor growth, with recurrent tumors nearly always resistant to cytotoxic medication.^{12,13} MGMT
146 methylation thus acts as a strong predictor of both TMZ response and OS.^{9,12,14,15}

147 However, O6-methylguanine lesions comprise ~5% of all TMZ-generated adducts, with
148 the rest comprised of N3-methyladenine (~9%) and N7-methylguanine (>70%), which are acted
149 upon by BER.^{16,17} Here, methyl groups in mutagenic adducts undergo cleavage of glycosidic bond
150 by methylpurine DNA glycosylase (MPG), thereby generating apurinic/apyrimidinic (AP) sites.¹⁷
151 AP endonucleases (APE1/APEX1) then cleave the phosphodiester bond 5'- to the AP site. The
152 resultant single-strand breaks (SSBs) are repaired by DNA polymerases through either non-
153 displacing (short-patch) or displacing (long-patch) synthesis.¹⁸ Disruption of any step in this
154 process results in BER dysfunction leaving adducts unrepaired and tumor cells at increased risk of
155 apoptosis driven by double-strand breaks (DSBs).¹⁷

156 TRC102 (methoxyamine hydrochloride) is a small molecule BER inhibitor that binds to
157 the sugar aldehyde at AP sites and prevents APEX1 from recognizing the damaged DNA site,
158 thereby leaving the DNA unrepaired.¹⁹⁻²¹ TRC102's BER inhibition sensitizes both MMR-
159 deficient and MMR-proficient tumor cells to methylating agents and thus potentiates TMZ
160 cytotoxicity through induced SSBs and DSBs.¹⁹⁻²¹ Cancer cells treated with TMZ produce N⁷-mG
161 and N³-mA DNA adducts, which activate BER to generate AP sites. TRC102 binds these sites
162 covalently to form structurally modified AP sites resistant to APEX1's repair activity. This leads
163 to targeting by topoisomerase II which induces double-strand breaks in DNA leading to tumor cell

164 apoptosis and illustrating a potential mechanism of synthetic lethality.²² This mechanism has been
165 shown to reverse TMZ resistance in preclinical models.^{21,23} Work in human glioma cell lines has
166 demonstrated that MPG overexpression greatly sensitizes tumor cells to temozolomide via BER
167 inhibition through TRC102, but the latter is overturned by overexpression of BER-rate-limiting
168 enzyme DNA polymerase β .²⁴ Higher MPG levels lead to increased binding sites for TRC102.
169 MPG overexpression and BER blockade thus sensitize tumor cells to TMZ in a polymerase β -
170 dependent fashion, indicating that MPG expression levels may predict TMZ potentiating activity
171 of TRC102.²⁴ In CD133+ GBM stem cell xenograft mice models, TRC+TMZ significantly
172 improved OS (median OS not reached after 230 days) versus TRC102 alone (79 days), saline
173 controls (75 days, $P < 0.001$), and TMZ alone (120 days, $P < 0.01$) [Data from laboratory of Andrew
174 Sloan, Case Comprehensive Cancer Center (CCCC), Cleveland, US; **Supplementary Figure S1**].

175 Given this strong preclinical rationale, the TRC102+TMZ combination therapy has been
176 explored in initial trials. A phase I dose-escalation trial (NCT00892385) of IV TRC102 and oral
177 TMZ in patients with advanced solid tumors and lymphomas, had indicated minimal toxicity and
178 no DLTs of combination therapy, with the maximum tolerated dose (MTD) being 150 mg IV daily
179 on day 1 and 200 mg/m² oral on days 1-5 for TRC102 and TMZ respectively, in combination
180 therapy.²⁵ TRC102 pharmacokinetics were linear and unaffected by TMZ, with trialists
181 recommending further investigation in tumors with demonstrated TMZ activity.²⁵ The present trial
182 was therefore planned in rGBM patients, based on the significance of TMZ resistance in this
183 patient population along with a significant unmet need. Additionally, gliomas have upregulated
184 levels of APEX1, whose blockade leads to BER inhibition and greater sensitivity to TMZ.

185 Investigators in the National Cancer Institute (NCI) Adult Brain Tumor Consortium
186 (ABTC) hypothesized that oral TRC102 can be safely co-administered with TMZ in patients with

187 rGBM and that TRC102 can augment DNA damage caused by TMZ, resulting in anti-rGBM
188 responses. Therefore, a multicenter, phase 2 trial, named BERT, was planned and conducted by
189 ABTC investigators to investigate the efficacy and safety of TRC102+TMZ therapy in patients
190 with rGBM.

191 **Methods**

192 *Study Design, Ethics, and Conduct*

193 This study was a non-randomized, pre-registered (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier:
194 NCT02395692), multicenter, two-arm, two-stage Phase 2 efficacy trial, which was conducted in
195 the US, and reported following the Consolidated Standards Of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) 2010
196 guidance.²⁶ The study was conducted through the National Cancer Institute (NCI) Adult Brain
197 Tumor Consortium (Reference Code: ABTC-1402), whose predecessor was the New Approaches
198 for Brain Tumor Therapy (NABTT) Consortium.^{27,28} The Key Resources Table for all associated
199 data may be accessed in Supplementary Table S1. The trial protocol is available in the
200 Supplementary Appendix S1.

201 The trial was conducted after approval by the Protocol Review Committee of the Cancer
202 Therapy and Evaluation Program (CTEP Reference Number: PABTC_1402_R03PAPP01) and
203 fulfillment of relevant local and national regulations, guidance, and policies, including the
204 Declaration of Helsinki. The trial documents, including all amendments, were approved by the
205 local Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) of all involved trial sites, including Johns Hopkins
206 University (coordinating center), Cleveland Clinic, Ohio (IRB Reference number 15-1529), Henry
207 Ford Health System (IRB Reference number 10163), University of Pittsburgh Medical Center
208 (IRB Reference number PRO16020302; UPCI #15-171), University of California Los Angeles

209 (IRB Reference number 15-001680) and Wake Forest University Health Sciences (IRB Reference
210 number IRB00034709). Written informed consent was provided prior to participation.

211 *Study Objectives and Outcomes*

212 Arm 1 included bevacizumab-naïve patients with the first recurrence of GBM following
213 radiation therapy and TMZ. Arm 2 included bevacizumab-refractory GBM patients with an
214 unlimited number of prior therapy regimens. The primary objective of arm 1 was to estimate the
215 efficacy of oral TMZ+TRC102 as measured by overall objective response rate (ORR) according
216 to the RANO criteria, with secondary endpoints being median PFS, PFS-6, OS, and toxicity.²⁹
217 Patients were evaluated at the end of every 2 treatment cycles (every 8 weeks). Assessment of
218 response/progression was first performed at each institution by the local radiologist using RANO
219 criteria. MRI scans of subjects showing tumor response were centrally reviewed by a
220 neuroradiologist who independently assessed tumor sizes and computed percent tumor regression.

221 Arm 2 would open if arm 1 met ORR criteria, whose primary objective was evaluation of
222 ORR in bevacizumab-refractory GBM patients, after administration of TRC102 and TMZ. The
223 secondary endpoints of arm 2, similar to arm 1, were median PFS, PFS-6, OS, and toxicity.

224 The exploratory objective was to investigate the relationship between survival and biologic
225 markers in tumor tissue, including MGMT, MPG, genomics, and transcriptomics, a design similar
226 to the study of Weeks et al.³⁰ N-methylpurine DNA glycosylase (MPG) overexpression and
227 inhibition of BER are associated with the sensitization of glioma cells to TMZ.²⁴

228 *Study Participants*

229 Patients with glioblastoma (GBM) who had progressed after surgical resection, external
230 beam radiation, and adjuvant TMZ were included, with the representativeness of study participants
231 further described in **Supplementary Table S2**. Further eligibility criteria included age ≥ 18 years,

TRC102 with Temozolomide for Recurrent Glioblastoma (BERT)

232 with Karnofsky Performance Status (KPS) $\geq 60\%$ (i.e. be able to care for himself/herself with
233 occasional help from others), adequate organ and marrow function defined as absolute neutrophil
234 count $> 1,500/\mu\text{L}$, platelets $> 100,000/\mu\text{L}$, hemoglobin $> 9 \text{ g/dL}$, total bilirubin \leq institutional upper
235 limit of normal (iULN), AST/ALT ≤ 4 times iULN, creatinine \leq iULN, creatinine clearance > 60
236 ml/min/1.73m^2 for patients with creatinine levels above iULN, and APTT or PTT ≤ 1.5 times
237 iULN. Patients were eligible for the trial if they were 12 weeks from the completion of
238 radiotherapy and six weeks from nitrosourea chemotherapy. Additionally, while Response
239 Assessment in Neuro-Oncology (RANO) criteria were not explicitly specified in patient eligibility,
240 the trial was performed at established cancer centers with quaternary care brain tumor programs,
241 where RANO criteria were used as a standard.

242 Patients with concurrent malignancy were excluded, except for curatively treated basal or
243 squamous cell carcinoma of the skin or carcinoma in situ of the cervix, breast, or bladder, with the
244 patient disease-free for ≥ 5 years. Other exclusion criteria were treatment with any other
245 investigational agent, treatment with anticoagulants, active uncontrolled intercurrent illness,
246 and/or prior gastrointestinal (GI) surgery or GI disease that might interfere with the absorption of
247 TRC102. Pregnant subjects were also excluded from the study, given the potential teratogenic or
248 abortifacient effect of TRC102. No exclusion to this study was based on race or ethnicity.

249 *Study Intervention*

250 TRC102 (methoxyamine) is a small molecule BER-inhibitor developed by investigators
251 from CCCC (Cleveland, Ohio, US) and an oral formulation was supplied by NCI Division of
252 Cancer Treatment and Diagnosis (DCTD, RRID:SCR_004196), under a collaborative agreement
253 with Traccon Pharmaceuticals, Inc. (San Diego, CA).

TRC102 with Temozolomide for Recurrent Glioblastoma (BERT)

254 TRC102 and TMZ were administered orally, based on prior clinical trials. While the trial
255 at CCCC (NCT00892385) had dosed TRC102 intravenously,²⁵ the NCI phase I trial in relapsed
256 solid tumors and lymphomas had dosed TRC102 orally on days 1-5 of a 28-day cycle
257 (NCT01851369), along with oral TMZ.³¹ The phase 1 trial had determined the maximum tolerated
258 dose (MTD) as 150 mg TRC102 and 150 mg/m² TMZ. Based on these findings, dosing in the
259 current trial was planned, where TMZ was dosed based on body surface area at 150 mg/m²/day,
260 while TRC102 was dosed at flat 150mg/day, both administered orally once a day for 5 consecutive
261 days, repeated every 28 days, with weekly evaluation of blood counts. No dose modifications were
262 required.

263 Enrollment was done using the Oncology Patient Enrollment Network (OPEN) and
264 supported by the NCI Cancer Trials Support Unit (CTSU). Treatment was administered on an
265 outpatient basis. Patients were allowed to receive other medications that the investigator deemed
266 to be medically necessary, with the specific exception of non-protocol-specified chemotherapy,
267 radiotherapy, anti-neoplastic biological therapy, or other investigational agents.

268 *Molecular Testing*

269 Tumor MGMT status was obtained at individual treatment sites. The results of routinely
270 used methods for routine MGMT promoter methylation testing (for instance, methylation-specific
271 PCR or quantitative PCR), as per institutional standards, were considered acceptable. Gene
272 expression analyses were performed by the Translational Genomics Research Institute (TGen, City
273 of Hope, CA, RRID:SCR_011581). Immunohistochemistry for MPG expression was performed
274 on pretreatment paraffin-embedded sections from representative areas of tumors using rabbit
275 polyclonal anti-MPG antibody (Sigma-Aldrich Cat# HPA006531, RRID: AB_1854075) at 1:800
276 dilution with citrate buffer antigen retrieval MACH 4 HRP Polymer (BioCare Medical, Pacheco,

277 CA) and Betazoid DABKit (BioCare Medical, Pacheco, CA) detection method. MPG expression
278 was graded from 0 to 2+. Slides were reviewed in a blinded fashion by a neuropathologist. RNA
279 sequencing was performed, under a separate IRB restricted to specific trial sites, on tumor tissue
280 from treatment-naïve recurrent GBM patients. From the samples received for genomic analyses at
281 a secondary site (TGen, City of Hope, CA), sequencing was performed on samples with
282 appropriate RNA integrity numbers in order to understand the context of vulnerability to TRC102
283 and TMZ in recurrent GBM patients.

284

285 *Analysis of Clinical Data*

286 The primary objective was to test the hypothesis of whether the combination therapy of
287 TRC and TMZ would achieve a 30% overall radiographic response rate (partial response and
288 complete response) of TRC102+TMZ in patients with the first recurrence of GBM, based on
289 criteria set by NCI-CTEP protocol review committee.

290 A two-stage (mini-max) design was used to discriminate between true response rates of no
291 more than 13% and at least 30% with 85% statistical power and a 10% false positive rate in arm
292 1. The maximum trial size would be set at 31 evaluable patients. If at least seven responses (at
293 least 22.5%) were observed among the 31 evaluable patients, this regimen would be considered
294 worthy of further testing in this disease. If no more than two responses (no more than 10.5%) were
295 observed among the initial 19 patients, the study would be terminated early for futility.

296 Arm 2 for bevacizumab-refractory patients was warranted only if the first arm met its
297 efficacy criteria. A two-stage design for Arm 2 with 90% statistical power and 5% false positive
298 rate to test the hypothesis of a clinical benefit of 30% radiographic response against a 10% overall

299 response rate of TRC102+TMZ in patients with multiple prior therapies and were bevacizumab-
300 refractory, treated with TRC102 and TMZ, and continued on bevacizumab.

301 Nineteen GBM patients at first recurrence were enrolled and included in the analysis (arm
302 1 and stage 1 only). The time of progression-free survival was calculated from the date treatment
303 started to the date of disease progression or censored during analysis if the patient was free of
304 progressive disease. The two longest surviving patients received extended follow-up after the
305 dataset lock. OS duration was calculated from the start date of treatment to the date of death or
306 censoring at the time of analysis if patients were alive. Baseline patient characteristics were
307 summarized using standard descriptive summaries. The PFS-6 proportion was estimated using
308 binomial distribution with a 95% confidence interval. OS and PFS were estimated using the
309 Kaplan–Meier method, with confidence intervals constructed using the method of Brookmeyer-
310 Crowley.³² All adverse events were graded according to Common Terminology Criteria for
311 Adverse Events (CTCAE) version 4.0. Adverse events deemed to be possibly, probably, or
312 definitely attributed to TRC102+TMZ were summarized using descriptive statistics. Log-rank test
313 was used to explore the survival differences between GBM patients with MGMT-methylated and
314 unmethylated tumors. All statistical analyses were performed using SAS version 9.4 (SAS
315 Institute, Cary, NC, RRID:SCR_008567).

316

317 *Analysis of Molecular Data*

318 Clinical outcomes were correlated with tumor molecular features, including MGMT and
319 MPG status, and reported in accordance with elements of the REMARK reporting framework.³³
320 After RNA sequencing of tumor tissue obtained at baseline, functional class scoring was pursued
321 using Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) and single sample GSEA. For this, differentially

322 expressed genes (DEGs) were analyzed using DESeq2 GSEA (RRID:SCR_015687;
323 RRID:SCR_003199). This was applied to transform the expression profiles into enrichment scores
324 for the 'HALLMARK_DNA_REPAIR' gene set (44 founder gene sets) from the Molecular
325 Signatures Database (MSigDB, RRID:SCR_016863), using methods we have described
326 previously.³⁴ GSEA and clustering analysis were used to explore and assign candidate mechanistic
327 signatures of distinct vulnerability to TRC102+TMZ.

328 We also evaluated patients against a set of 39 manually curated gene sets to understand if
329 these gene sets could also differentiate responder and non-responder patients. These gene sets, in
330 MSigDB, were associated with “DNA Repair”, “Base Excision Repair”, “Nucleotide Excision
331 Repair”, TP53 signaling (given its role in driving BER signaling), tumor mutational burden for
332 GBM, and chromosomal aberrations, given the association between genomic instability and DNA
333 damage response.

334 Single sample GSEA was performed in R using Bioconductor package
335 (RRID:SCR_006442) using methods described by Gu et al.³⁵ Signaling Pathway Impact Analysis
336 (SPIA) integrating differentially expressed genes and their log fold changes with signaling
337 pathways topology was performed as described by Tarca and colleagues.³⁶ Comparative analyses
338 were performed with datasets from the Clinical Proteomic Tumor Analysis Consortium (CPTAC,
339 RRID:SCR_017135), The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA, RRID:SCR_003193), and the
340 Circulating Cell-free Genome Atlas study (CCGA, NCT02889978).

341

342 ***Data Availability***

343 The final amended study protocol is available in Supplementary Appendix S13. This
344 study, a clinical trial, generated individual patient data (IPD), which were used to create the

345 figures and the tables in the main manuscript. Additional analyses carried out on publicly
346 available datasets are reported in the supplementary figures S3-S7. Deidentified IPD is not being
347 made available publicly given the small sample size (N=19), the relatively low incidence of
348 glioblastoma (compared to other systemic malignancies), and the novelty of the study
349 medication, all of which together place limits on assurance of patient privacy and confidentiality.
350 IPD data, including source data for figures and tables, informed consent form, and clinical study
351 report, will be made available to qualified researchers for IPD meta-analysis upon reasonable
352 request for up to six years after publication. Proposals should be directed to the corresponding
353 author at manmeetA@baptisthealth.net.

354 **Results**

355 The trial began patient enrollment in January 2016 and finished enrolling in June 2016.
356 Nineteen patients were enrolled in arm 1 in the first stage of the trial, i.e., TRC102+TMZ for
357 bevacizumab-naïve recurrent GBM (rGBM). The median age of patients was 60 years (range 48-
358 76). The median KPS at baseline was 80 (range 70-90). 53% of the patients were female, and 95%
359 were white. The median number of treatment cycles was 2 (range 1-12). The baseline patient
360 attributes and the disease characteristics are summarized in **Table 1** and compared with prior
361 literature in **Supplementary Table S2**. No dose modification was performed for any recruited
362 patient.

363

364 ***Clinical Outcomes***

365 Among the 19 patients included in the analysis, 17 had died by the time of the dataset lock.
366 The study did not meet its prespecified response rate criteria and was terminated after arm 1/stage
367 1. Hence, arm 2 did not open for accrual. At the time of the planned database lock, the median OS

368 was 11.1 months (95%CI 8.2-17.9 months) and the median PFS was 1.9 months (95%CI 1.8-3.7
369 months) (**Figure 1**). PFS at six months was 10.5% (N=2/19, 95%CI: 1.3-33.1%). Five patients
370 were found to have an OS of ≥ 20 months. The combination of TRC102 and TMZ was safe and
371 well tolerated. Overall AEs that were possibly, probably, or definitely related to either TRC102,
372 TMZ, or both are listed in **Supplementary Table S3**. Most treatment-related AEs were CTCAE
373 Grade 1 or 2, with only two CTCAE Grade 3 lymphopenias and one CTCAE Grade 4
374 thrombocytopenia.

375 There were two patients deemed ‘extended survivors’, where extended follow-up beyond
376 the dataset lock date indicated a PFS of ≥ 17 months and OS ≥ 32 months. Both were aged >55
377 years, had KPS of 80, and had IDH wild-type and MGMT promoter methylated tumors. Following
378 treatment in the trial, one patient had a PFS of 29 months and was alive at 60 months when lost to
379 follow-up, while the other had a PFS of 17 months and an OS of 32 months.

380

381 ***Correlation with MPG and MGMT expression***

382 MGMT promoter methylation status was available for all included patients. 14/19 patients
383 had MGMT unmethylated tumors. The median OS of methylated patients was 30.2 months
384 (95%CI 9.5-NA), and in unmethylated patients was 9.9 months (95%CI 5.8-13) (P=0.02). Median
385 PFS in methylated patients was 5.6 months (95%CI 1.9-NA) and in unmethylated patients was 1.9
386 months (95%CI 1.8-2.3) (P=0.003).

387 Tissue for MPG expression was available in 14 cases. Nuclear positivity for MPG via IHC
388 was identified in eight patients (1+ in five, 2+ in three). MPG expression was negative in six.
389 Stratified analysis of PFS and OS using MPG expression status demonstrated an inverse
390 relationship. Median OS was 11.1 months (95%CI 3.7-NA, N=3) for 2+ MPG expression, 14.5

391 months (95%CI 7.9-32.3) for 1+ MPG expression and 17.9 months (95%CI 9.3-30.2) for absent
392 expression (P=0.05). Median PFS was 1.9 months (95%CI 1.4-NA) for 2+ MPG expression, 2.8
393 months (95%CI 1.9-NA) for 1+ MPG expression, and 3.7 months (95%CI 1.8-5.6) for absent
394 expression (P=0.07). In the 5 patients where MPG expression could not be evaluated due to trial
395 logistics, the median OS was 8.1 months (95%CI 2.0-10.2), while the median PFS was 1.8 months
396 (1.6-1.9). However, one ‘extended survivor’ had 1+ MPG expression while the other had 2+ MPG
397 expression.

398

399 *Translational Findings*

400 Adequate quantity and quality of RNA samples were available for transcriptome profiling
401 from the tumor tissue of 7 patients. In the two patients deemed ‘extended survivors’ (PFS \geq 17
402 months), preliminary analysis on RNA sequencing data revealed significant enrichment for DNA
403 damage response (DDR) pathways (MSigDB) (**Figure 2A**), chromosomal instability gene
404 signatures (CIN70 and CIN25) (**Figure 2B**), and aneuploidy that includes proliferative gene
405 signature (PCNA25) (**Figure 2C**). Another patient with OS of 30.2 months and PFS of 5.5 months
406 (patient ID 0205, IDH wild type, MGMT methylated) had some borderline expression for DDR.
407 Extended disease control with TRC102 + TMZ combination therapy was found independent of the
408 molecular subtype of glioblastoma (mesenchymal, classical, or proneural) (**Figure 3A**). Single
409 sample GSEA with hierarchical clustering of thirteen genesets segregated these ‘extended
410 survivors’ from those whose disease progressed early (**Figure 3B**). Genesets encompassing
411 nucleotide excision repair featured prominently.

412 Analysis of 178 GBM patients (RNASeq) in the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) database
413 using 44 founder gene sets in HALLMARK_DNA_REPAIR (MSigDB) also demonstrates that

414 9.6% (N=17) of glioblastoma patients in TCGA have hyperactivation of DNA Damage Response
415 signaling pathways (**Figure 3**).

416 Focusing on BER-specific gene sets, which included MPG expression and 18 other genes
417 culled in the REACTOME (**Figure 4A**) or 38 other genes culled in KEGG (**Figure 4B**), did not
418 clearly segregate the extended survivors from other patients. Meanwhile, cluster analysis using 39
419 manually selected genesets, including DNA Repair, Base Excision Repair, and Nucleotide
420 Excision Repair, was performed, which segregated extended survivors from those with worse
421 disease course (**Figure 4C**).

422 Signaling Pathway Impact Analysis (SPIA) using differentially expressed genes and their
423 log fold changes integrated with signaling pathways topology uncovered pathways differentiating
424 extended survivors from others (**Supplementary Figure S2**). Notable pathways inhibited in
425 ‘extended survivors’ include KEGG 5200 “Pathways in Cancer” (313 genes), KEGG 4810
426 “Regulation of actin cytoskeleton” (204 genes), KEGG 5218 “Melanoma” (68 genes), and KEGG
427 4540 “Gap junction” (88 genes).

428 Comparative analyses done using cBioPortal, the TCGA database, the CCGA database,
429 and the CPTAC database provided additional insights into the interplay between MGMT and MPG
430 status (**Supplementary Figures S3 to S7**). A substantially high correlation was found between
431 mRNA Z-scores and protein abundance scores (Spearman’s coefficient 0.79, $P < 0.001$) for MGMT
432 but not for MPG (Spearman’s coefficient 0.15, $P = 0.15$) in the CPTAC database (**Supplementary**
433 **Figures S3 and S4**). The protein abundance scores of MGMT and MPG did not correlate well in
434 the CPTAC database (Spearman’s coefficient -0.10, $P = 0.317$) (**Supplementary Appendix S5**).
435 Meanwhile, mRNA co-expression values for MGMT and MPG were found to be well correlated
436 for primary GBM in the TCGA database (Spearman’s coefficient 0.51, $P < 0.001$) (**Supplementary**

437 **Appendix S6**), and for recurrent GBM in the CCGA database (Spearman's coefficient 0.58,
438 $P < 0.001$) (**Supplementary Appendix S7**).

439 **Discussion**

440 The past three decades have seen only a single efficacious drug being FDA-approved for
441 glioblastoma, i.e., temozolomide, with the vast majority of neuro-oncology clinical trials failing to
442 translate investigational therapies to the standard of care. Unlike other solid tumors, efficacious
443 drugs still remain unavailable after glioblastoma (GBM) recurrence, despite the thousands of
444 patients accrued to neuro-oncology trials worldwide.³⁷ Therefore, careful investigation into novel
445 therapeutics remain vital to improving outcomes for patients with progressive GBM.^{37,38} In this
446 work, we reported findings from a multicenter phase 2 clinical trial (BERT), along with correlative
447 transcriptomic analyses, of an investigational DNA base excision repair (BER) inhibitor TRC102,
448 combined with the DNA alkylating agent temozolomide for patients with bevacizumab-naïve
449 recurrent GBM at first relapse. The results of the trial confirm that TRC102, in combination with
450 TMZ, is safe, well-tolerated, and therapeutically feasible for patients with recurrent GBM. Trial
451 findings also provide insights into the context of tumor vulnerability to synthetic lethality
452 generated with a combination of a DNA damaging agent and DNA repair blockade, along with
453 indicating a potential for improved patient selection for therapeutic targeting through DNA
454 damage response (DDR) signature.

455 Given the extremely low rates of successful bench-to-bedside drug translations for
456 glioblastoma, optimizing the currently available treatments is a meaningful approach. TMZ
457 resistance is associated with the expression levels of DNA alkylating proteins and DNA repair
458 enzymes.³⁹ Significant efforts have been directed at sensitizing resistant tumors to currently
459 available cytotoxic therapies such as TMZ. Because the BER pathway is a principal cellular

460 process employed by malignant cells to reduce the cytotoxicity of alkylating agents, the
461 combination of TMZ with a BER inhibitor has been hypothesized to improve anti-tumor efficacy,
462 which was demonstrated preclinically (**Supplementary Figure S1**). This phase 2 trial depicts the
463 safety and feasibility of a first-in-class inhibitor of BER TRC102 combined with TMZ for patients
464 with GBM progressive after first-line therapy with TMZ and radiation therapy. Since the pre-
465 specified criteria were not met in the present study, the trial did not proceed to test TRC102 and
466 TMZ in bevacizumab-refractory tumors, a particularly treatment-refractory subset of
467 patients where all efforts to induce relevant disease stabilization have thus far failed. This failure
468 to demonstrate clinical efficacy may be seen in the background of a progressive disease where the
469 vast majority of trials fail to meet their primary endpoint. Here, the trial had >70% of patients with
470 MGMT unmethylated tumors, who were unlikely to respond to TMZ.⁴⁰ While efficacy here was
471 limited, the combination of TRC102 and TMZ may hold further potential in a biomarker-enriched
472 subset of patients. In the CCCC trial, Eads et al. had reported a lack of correlation between dose
473 level and either COMET assay outcome or response to therapy.⁴¹ However, their
474 pharmacodynamic assays had been performed on peripheral blood mononuclear cells, rather than
475 tumor tissue, which the investigators proposed assessing through quantitative assessment of AP
476 sites in tumor tissue.³⁹ In the current trial, a therapeutic vulnerability signature was detected by
477 sequencing tumor tissue obtained at initial diagnosis, i.e. prior to TRC102+TMZ therapy.

478 Here, TRC102 did not significantly potentiate TMZ-induced myelosuppression, and non-
479 hematologic toxicity was rare. This is consistent with the prior Case Comprehensive Cancer Center
480 (CCCC) trial,²⁵ and the NCI phase 1 trial,³¹ both trial reports published in full recently.^{41,42} The
481 CCCC trial had a mixed patient population including 29% colorectal, 16% lung, 13% pancreas,
482 8% head and neck, and 5% neuroendocrine cancers amongst others. Anemia occurred in half of

483 all enrolled patients, being majorly grade 1-2 and not associated with hemolysis. Eads et al. had
484 also reported a single occurrence of grade 4 thrombocytopenia amongst 38 patients,⁴¹ similar to
485 the current trial with one grade 4 thrombocytopenia. Meanwhile, of the 52 patients enrolled in the
486 NCI trial, 30% had colorectal cancer, 12% had ovarian cancer, 8% had mesothelioma, 6% had
487 breast cancer, and 6% had cholangiocarcinoma, among others.⁴² Here as well, most toxicities were
488 grade 1-2, with grade 3 or higher anemia hematologic toxicities including anemia in 10 patients,
489 lymphopenia in 6 patients, and thrombocytopenia in 3 patients (all grade 4).

490 Patients in this trial having MGMT methylated tumors had improved survival, consistent
491 with the prior literature on glioblastoma on the strong prognostic utility of MGMT silencing, the
492 critical role of DNA repair, and the utility of targeting DDR.^{40,43-44} Meanwhile, upon stratification
493 by MPG status, the median survival was longest in those lacking MPG expression, shorter in the
494 1+ expression group, and shortest in the 2+ expression cohort. Considerable literature exists on the
495 conflicting results regarding the role of MPG in tumor cell vulnerability to TMZ and the prognostic
496 significance of MPG expression in malignant gliomas. Fosmark et al. found a significant
497 association between high levels of MPG and improved OS,⁴⁵ consistent with the results from both
498 the TCGA dataset and *in-vitro* studies.^{24,46} However, this contrasts with other studies showing that
499 patients with MPG non-expression had a more favorable outcome.^{47,48} The latter is supported by
500 data from studies in patient-derived glioma cells, where high MPG expression correlated with a
501 TMZ-resistant phenotype.¹⁸ Confounding a simple direct mechanistic link between low MPG and
502 greater vulnerability to the genotoxic effects of TMZ, another report by Chou et al. in 2015
503 indicated lethal DDR activation by base lesions that trigger the ATM-Chk2 pathway.⁴⁹ We found
504 that while levels of MGMT and MPG mRNA are concordant for both primary and recurrent
505 glioblastoma (**Supplementary Figures S6 and S7**), this correlation fails to materialize at the level

506 of proteins, where MPG mRNA values do not correspond to MPG protein values (**Supplementary**
507 **Figure S4**), nor do MPG protein levels correspond to MGMT protein levels (**Supplementary**
508 **Figure S5**). This potentially supports the use of immunohistochemistry (IHC) for the detection of
509 MPG status in GBM, as performed here, instead of RNA sequencing. This contrasts with MGMT,
510 where protein abundance correlates well with mRNA expression (**Supplementary Figure S4**).
511 Overall, given the discordant results in our trial and as demonstrated in prior studies, MPG remains
512 a challenging biomarker for investigation, with likely several secondary mechanisms at play.<sup>18,24,45-
513 48</sup>

514 In this trial, analysis of transcriptomic genesets of BER alone (which include MPG
515 expression) did not segregate the extended survivors from other patients (**Figure 4B**). The
516 existence of multiple DNA-repair-related pathways potentially obscures the fine segregation of
517 extended survivors and also makes it challenging to interpret to what degree the differential
518 expression of each specific pathway contributes to the likelihood of therapeutic response. While
519 TRC102 inhibits the BER pathway, there may be off-target effects that account for *in vivo*
520 antiglioma activity. Further, the work by Chou et al, describing the lethal DDR activation by DNA
521 lesions triggering the ATM-Chk2 pathway, ties into the more recent work by Dmello and
522 colleagues implicating Chk2 expression by glioma cells with escape from recognition by CD8 T-
523 cells.^{49,50} BER inhibition in some glioblastoma patients may potentially have sensitization
524 consequences to immune cell attack of the tumor. Such off-target consequences as immune
525 sensitization in the clinical setting may be a source of the discordance related to biomarkers of
526 BER inhibition, including MPG protein levels and BER-specific genesets.⁵⁰

527 In this trial, two ‘extended survivors’ demonstrated substantial evidence of clinical benefit.
528 Not only did they meet the secondary endpoint of PFS at six months, but they also had considerably

529 longer duration of survival (32 months and 60 months) and durable disease control, as evident in
530 in PFS of ≥ 17 months. Both had MGMT promoter methylation which also contributed to reduced
531 levels of DNA repair in tumor cells. RNA sequencing of their tumor tissue revealed significant
532 enrichment for DNA damage response pathways, chromosomal instability gene signature, and
533 proliferative gene signature. These molecular signatures could serve as useful biomarkers to
534 identify GBM patients likely to respond to a DNA alkylating agent combined with a DNA repair
535 inhibitor.

536 Prospective clinical validation of a molecular signature that predicts vulnerability to DNA
537 repair inhibitors in malignant gliomas will have applications in other malignancies with resistance
538 to DNA damaging agents. The trial investigators are planning a biomarker-enriched clinical trial
539 where prospective validation of the DDR signature will be pursued. This proposed phase I/II trial
540 is planned to enroll newly diagnosed, MGMT methylated GBM patients with hyperactivated DDR
541 molecular signature at baseline. Post-resection, TRC102 will be administered, in a 3+3 dose-
542 escalation design, concurrently with temozolomide and focal radiation therapy. It is hypothesized
543 that these patients with hyperactivated DDR will potentially respond better to combinatorial
544 therapy of TRC102 and TMZ, both of which impact DNA repair pathways.

545 Finally, the use of a glioblastoma umbrella signature trial (GUST), which tests multiple
546 investigational arms based on optimal patient selection using biochemical and molecular attributes,
547 may represent a suitable strategy for employing a host of molecular signatures to stratify patients
548 into various arms based on their likelihood of response.^{28,37,51} We have recently utilized semi-
549 supervised machine learning approaches on the TCGA database to identify signatures of
550 vulnerability for GBM. Using Entropy-Regularized Logistic Regression (ERLR), a predictive
551 model was developed based on both genomics and transcriptomics, transforming the unclassified

552 TCGA GBM patients into self-labeled datasets with the highest likelihood of response.⁵² This
553 permitted a virtual/mock stratification of >50% of the dataset's patients into at least one of four
554 treatment arms, having an elevated likelihood of response to TRC102 (DNA BER inhibitor),
555 arsenic trioxide (pleiotropic action), selinexor (exportin-1 inhibitor),⁵³ or pevonediostat
556 (neddylation inhibitor).⁵⁴ Use of innovative trial designs will likely be critical to success in the
557 extremely challenging space of GBM.^{28,37,51}

558 *Limitations of the Study*

559 First, given the need to demonstrate initial utility in a phase 2 trial, logistical and funding
560 requirements precluded the pursuit of a randomized controlled investigation. Second, the trial's
561 second arm did not open for accrual as the first arm did not meet prespecified criteria, thus limiting
562 definitive conclusions related to the efficacy of this novel medication. Third, a lack of data on
563 several molecular markers of GBM, now considered well-established as part of routine care, could
564 not be fully collected as several ABTC investigators changed institutions. Despite best efforts,
565 challenges related to tumor tissue access precluded the tallying of patient data regarding these
566 genetic markers from some of these institutions. Fourth, the transcriptomic analysis of tumors was
567 done on tissue collected at initial diagnosis, which may be of mixed utility in depicting the
568 transcriptome of these tumors at the time of recurrence when these patients were enrolled in the
569 clinical trial. However, since the pre-therapy transcriptomic data was available, it did permit the
570 prospective identification of the subset of patients with hyperactivated DNA damage response who
571 would potentially benefit from TRC102+TMZ combination therapy. Finally, the
572 representativeness of tumor tissue transcriptomics is confounded by the complexity of the full
573 complement of host cells along with tumor cells in resected tissue as well as the widely appreciated
574 heterogeneity of GBM.

575 **Conclusions**

576 DNA base excision repair inhibitor TRC102, in combination with DNA damaging agent
577 TMZ, is safe and well-tolerated in patients with recurrent or progressive GBM. A hyperactivated
578 DNA damage response (DDR) molecular signature at baseline in GBM patients is associated with
579 extended disease control on-therapy with TRC102 and TMZ, which needs prospective validation
580 in a future clinical trial.

581

582 **Abbreviations**

583	ABTC	Adult Brain Tumor Consortium
584	BER	Base Excision Repair
585	DDR	DNA Damage Response
586	GBM	Glioblastoma
587	MGMT	Methyl-Guanyl Methyl-Transferase
588	MTD	Maximum Tolerated Dose
589	NCI	National Cancer Institute
590	OS	Overall Survival
591	PFS	Progression-Free Survival
592	TMZ	Temozolomide

593

594 **DECLARATIONS:**

595

596 **Ethics approval and consent to participate:** The trial was conducted in accordance with all
597 relevant regulations and guidelines, including the declaration of Helsinki. Ethics approval was
598 provided by the local Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) of all involved trial sites, including
599 Johns Hopkins University (coordinating center), Cleveland Clinic, Ohio (IRB Reference number
600 15-1529), Henry Ford Health System (IRB Reference number 10163), University of Pittsburgh
601 Medical Center (IRB Reference number PRO16020302; UPCI #15-171), University of
602 California Los Angeles (IRB Reference number 15-001680) and Wake Forest University Health
603 Sciences (IRB Reference number IRB00034709). Written informed consent for participation was
604 obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

605 **Consent for publication:** Consent for publication of the findings of the trial was obtained.

606 **Inclusion and Diversity:** We support inclusive, diverse, and equitable conduct of research.

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TRC102 with Temozolomide for Recurrent Glioblastoma (BERT)

616 Molecular Investigation, MSA, MC, ML, MEB, YH, SP, SR, HD, TW; Statistical Analysis, XY;
617 Writing – Original Draft Preparation, MSA, XY, AO; Writing – Review & Editing, MSA, XY,
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623

624 **Competing Interests:**

625

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627 GSK, Xoft, Nuvation, Cellularity, SDP Oncology, Apollomics, Prelude, Janssen, Tocagen,
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629 Systems, Cairn Therapeutics, Anheart Therapeutics, Theraguix, Menarini Ricerche, Sumitomo
630 Pharma Oncology, Autem therapeutics, GT Medical Technologies. *Scientific Advisory Board:*
631 Cairn Therapeutics, Pyramid Biosciences, Modifi biosciences., Bugworks. *Stock shareholder:*
632 Mimivax, Cytodyn, MedInnovate Advisors LLC, Trisalus Lifesciences

633

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638 (Inst), Apollomics (Inst), Vigeo Therapeutics (Inst), Global Coalition for Adaptive Research
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654 *Sapience, Servier, Sagimet, Vascular Biogenics, VBI Vaccines*

655

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657

658

659 **Main Manuscript Tables and Figures:**

660

661 **Table 1:** Baseline patient characteristics at enrollment in the ABTC-1402 Phase 2 Trial.

Characteristics	Values
Patients Enrolled (N)	19
Age (years) - Median (range)	59.6 (48-76)
Sex – N (%)	
Male	9 (47%)
Female	10 (53%)
Race – N (%)	
White	18 (95%)
Non-White	1 (5%)
Initial Surgical Procedure – N (%)	
Resection	16 (84%)
Biopsy	3 (16%)
Histologic Diagnosis – N (%)	
Glioblastoma	19 (100%)
Karnofsky Performance status - N (%)	
90	7 (37%)
80	9 (47%)
70	3 (16%)
Steroid usage - N (%)	
Yes	6 (32%)
No	13 (68%)
Prior Relapses - N (%)	
One relapse	19 (100%)
MGMT Promoter Methylation - N (%)	
Methylated	5 (26%)
Unmethylated	14 (74%)
MPG expression - N (%)	
2+ Expression	3 (16%)
1+ Expression	5 (26%)
Absent	6 (32%)
Not Available	5 (26%)

662 *N, Number; MPG, Methylpurine DNA-glycosylase.*

663

TRC102 with Temozolomide for Recurrent Glioblastoma (BERT)

664 **Figure 1:** Kaplan-Meier survival curves for overall survival (OS) and progression-free survival
 665 (PFS) in the BERT trial. The curves do not capture the extended follow-up of two extended
 666 survivors beyond the data lock.

Figure 1

667

668

669

670 **Figure 2:** RNA sequencing and Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) of tumor tissue of
 671 patients whose tissue was available and had a reasonable RNA Integrity Number. This included
 672 two patients (0210 and 0208), deemed ‘extended survivors’, who had PFS of 17 and 29 months.
 673 Both were MGMT methylated. Transcriptomics was performed on tissue received at the initial
 674 surgical procedure. **(2A)** Hierarchical cluster analysis using 44 genesets in
 675 HALLMARK_DNA_REPAIR (MSigDB) segregated extended survivors from others. Extended
 676 survivors (PFS ≥ 17 months) demonstrated higher baseline expression of DNA Damage_response
 677 (DDR) signature. Patient 0205 with a borderline signature had a PFS of 5.5 months. **(2B)** Cluster
 678 analysis using chromosomal instability-related genes (CIN70 and CIN25) segregated individuals
 679 with the longest PFS from others. **(2C)** Cluster analysis using proliferation-related genes
 680 (PCNA25) poorly segregated individuals with the longest PFS from others.

Figure 2

681

682

683 **Figure 3:** Additional findings on gene set enrichment analysis from the seven patients sequenced
 684 in the current trial and the data of glioblastoma patients in the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA).
 685 **(3A)** Extended disease control on-therapy with TRC102+TMZ combination therapy was found
 686 independent of glioblastoma molecular subtypes (mesenchymal, proneural, and classical). **(3B)**
 687 ssGSEA on transcriptomic data from seven patients was performed, with Log2 expression of
 688 transcripts in thirteen genesets including genesets encompassing nucleotide excision repair,
 689 segregates extended survivors (0210 and 0208) from others, with the patient with the borderline
 690 signature (0205) having a PFS of 5.5 months. **(3C)** RNASeq analysis of 178 GBM patients in the
 691 TCGA database using 44 DNA Damage Response founder gene sets (MSigDB) demonstrates
 692 that 9.6% (N=17) of glioblastoma patients have hyper-activation of DNA Damage Response
 693 signaling pathways.

Figure 3

694

695 **Figure 4:** Hierarchical cluster analysis of transcriptomics of tumor tissue from newly diagnosed
 696 seven patients with recurrent GBM enrolled in NCT02395692 for base excision repair (BER)
 697 geneset. **(4A)** Cluster analysis using 19 genes in REACTOME BER geneset. **(4B)** Cluster
 698 analysis using 39 genes in the KEGG BER gene set. **(4C)** Cluster analysis using 39 manually
 699 selected genesets in the MSigDB database segregated longer surviving patients [‘extended
 700 survivors’ (0208 and 0210) and another with some benefit (0205)] from patients with much
 701 lower duration of PFS and OS.

702

703

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